

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

A SNORD regulated by NOD2 and perturbed by NOD2 mutation.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Citations

1. Askarian-Amiri, M.E., Crawford, J., French, J.D., Smart, C.E., Smith, M.A., Clark, M.B., Ru, K., Mercer, T.R., Thompson, E.R., Lakhani, S.R. and Vargas, A.C., 2011. SNORD-host RNA Zfas1 is a regulator of mammary development and a potential marker for breast cancer. *Rna*, 17(5), pp.878-891.